

Public Report on EBRAINS-Italy functionalities and use

Project title: EBRAINS-Italy- European Brain ReseArch INfrastructures-Italy
CUP: B51E22000150006

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This report illustrates the EBRAINS-Italy functionalities and use, made available through the EBRAINS-Italy website (<https://ebrains-italy.eu>) that is a comprehensive digital platform that provides access to the infrastructure's information, data, models, tools and services. The website is designed with user accessibility in mind and features responsive design and user-friendly interface and navigation layout. To guarantee the largest audience, the adopted language is English. The portal provides contact information for general inquiries and opportunities to join the EBRAINS-Italy network, fostering collaboration among researchers, institutions, and industry partners.

Dedicated pages provide information and resources about the consortium, structure, organization, mission and objectives of the EBRAINS-Italy project:

<https://ebrains-italy.eu/>, <https://www.ebrains-italy.eu/about-us>, <https://www.ebrains-italy.eu/project>,
<https://www.ebrains-italy.eu/coordination-team>, <https://www.ebrains-italy.eu/resources/research-teams>

The outcomes of the project are made available as research products, services and resources. These span a plethora of scientific topics, including: a) Neurodegenerative Diseases: Research on aging, epilepsy, Alzheimer's, and other neurological disorders; b) Brain Modeling: development of computational models to simulate brain functions; c) Experimental Labs: access to facilities for brain research; d) Innovation: Support for technological advancements in neuroscience. A map and search tool allow users to explore the facilities across Italy, providing information on their locations and the services they offer.

Each scientific resource is individual or comprises an ensemble of products (e.g., dataset, code scripts, ...). Resources are provided with dedicated guidelines and tutorials for their use and are grouped by the following three categories:

- Data: <https://ebrains-italy.eu/resources/datasets>
- Models: <https://ebrains-italy.eu/resources/models>
- Analysis tools: <https://ebrains-italy.eu/resources/analysis-tools>

A list of components (i.e., project outcomes) and scientific articles is available on a dedicated page: <https://ebrains-italy.eu/resources/components-and-dissemination>. More information on scientific publications are also available on the Publication page: <https://ebrains-italy.eu/resources/publications>.

National labs, data services and research facilities are made available through specific access programs: <https://ebrains-italy.eu/survey>.

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